

Robust 4D awareness via diffusion adaptation over Connected and Automated vehicles

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Abstract—In this paper, we focus on enhancing the 4D situational awareness in a swarm of Connected and Automated vehicles, employing information diffusion against unsuccessful object detection. More specifically, in the perception layer we exploit model compression and acceleration techniques for the efficient execution of relevant deep learning models, and determine different probabilities of detection success. Afterwards, we integrate these success indicators in the localization layer of nodes and by information diffusion we verify increased global location awareness against missing detections. A variety of simulated experiments performed in KITTI dataset, as well as CARLA simulator, indicate that the localization layer is able to address highly efficient the missing detections for each accelerated model, effectively realizing the vision of distributed swarm intelligence.

Index Terms—CAVs, Perception, Localization, Awareness

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays billion of devices are connecting to the internet, leading to the formation of Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs) swarm systems, including but not limited to multi-robot groups, fleets of ground and underwater autonomous vehicles, multiple Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), etc. The purpose of the swarm's nodes is to collectively perceive and analyze their surrounding environment in a distributed manner so as to improve reliability, scalability and safety or in more general, distributed swarm intelligence. Motivated by related automotive applications [1], this swarm intelligence architecture can be realized through a perception layer, which visually detects and identifies nearby objects, as well as a localization layer which is feeded by the previous one in order to provide positioning information. Note that perception layer usually comprises of visual sensors like LIDAR, Cameras, etc., and accelerated Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to meet real-time processing requirements. The localization layer, apart from standalone solutions like visual and LIDAR based odometry, satellite based systems, etc., is benefited by 5G communication protocols in order to receive and transmit relevant measurements and information. This concept of Cooperative Localization (CL) [2] has shown to be very promising in terms of location awareness accuracy of each node, and is adopted in this work.

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1) *Accelerated 3D scene analysis*: 3D object detection from LIDAR point clouds is mainly a data-driven task due to the lack of apparent structure in the data. Deep fully CNNs have been traditionally employed [3]–[8] in the literature since 2016, with the main evolutionary elements to concern i) the transformation of the 3D point cloud, ii) the network structure and iii) the utilization of feedback loops or abstraction layers for a multi scale feature extraction approach. Model Compression and Acceleration (MCA) [9]–[11] refers to a family of approaches which produce efficient deep models in terms of the required resources (computational, storage) during the inference phase of its operation. This is achieved by transforming an original, pre-trained deep model of high complexity to a new reduced one.

2) *Cooperative Localization*: To realize CL, either probabilistic tracking or convex optimization algorithms can be employed [12]. Kalman Filtering and its non-linear variant Extended Kalman Filtering (EKF) has been used in literature for improving either self location of vehicles [13] or local awareness in multi-robot and vehicle groups [14], [15] in a distributed manner. Angular measurements have been employed in [16] to derive and minimize centralized convex cost functions, while the so-called distributed information diffusion based awareness schemes have been introduced in [17]. Multi Dimensional Scaling (MDS) is a renowned centralized optimization algorithm [18], [19], which through the euclidean distance matrix formulated by each pair of involved nodes, together with their self positioning measurements as anchors, is able to re-estimate accurate enough their positions. MDS will be used as a baseline CL method in this work.

To realize an effective intelligence architecture for CAVs system, we introduce for the first time a combined system of perception and localization layers which is robust against missing object detection, offering increased location estimation over time (4D awareness). The main contributions of the paper are as follows:

- A unified approach for perception and localization of CAVs using scene analysis accelerated modules and CL is proposed. Perception, through a 3D CNN model, feeds localization in order to robustify location awareness of nodes.
- The 3D CNN model achieves average precision for the Car class between 81.88% and 93.08% for different acceleration techniques and ratios. Integrating these scores of

detection in the localization layer, information diffusion based awareness proves to be much superior than state-of-the-art MDS against missing detections of nearby objects.

- Extensive and realistic simulation studies carried out in KITTI dataset and CARLA simulator verify the proposed system’s benefits in terms of detection success and robust awareness.

Outline: Section II introduces the system model; Sections III and IV present perception and localization layers; Section V is dedicated to numerical results and analysis, while Section VI concludes this work.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

Consider the swarm or cluster $\mathcal{C}^{(t)}$ of CAVs at an urban environment in Fig. 1. The cluster comprises of nodes, as well as the neighborhoods $\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}$ that each individual node i establishes together with its closest connected neighbors. The perception layer is responsible for providing scene analysis and understanding indicators employing visual and mechanic sensors, satellite based communication, etc. To be more specific, perception layer provides two types of measurements available to i at time instant t , assuming Gaussian measurement noise [20]:

- Self positioning:

$$\tilde{z}_{p,i}^{(t)} = \mathbf{x}_i^{(t)} + \mathbf{n}_p^{(t)}, \mathbf{n}_p^{(t)} \sim \mathcal{G}(0, \Sigma_p) \quad (1)$$

, where $\mathbf{x}_i^{(t)} = [x_i^{(t)} \ y_i^{(t)}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^2$ is the ground truth 2D position of i . Self positioning measurements are usually degraded by high enough drift (due to LIDAR or camera sensors) and measurement error (due to GNSS or IMU sensors).

- Relative observation:

$$\tilde{z}_{o,ij}^{(t)} = g(\mathbf{x}_i^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}_j^{(t)}) + n_o^{(t)}, n_o^{(t)} \sim \mathcal{G}(0, \sigma_o^2) \quad (2)$$

, including distance and angular measurements of (observer) i towards (target) neighbor j . In practice, for each detected object of the scene a 3D or 2D bounding box is formed, and then relative observations are extracted using the centroid of this very box.

Additionally, a data association sub-module is required to match the visually extracted relative observations with the self positions transmitted by each node, in order to effectively perform CL solutions. The well-known Hungarian algorithm can be used for this task. However, in realistic conditions $\tilde{z}_{o,ij}^{(t)}$ may not be able to be determined due to occlusion, harsh weather conditions, night environment, etc. Therefore, a probability λ of detection success should be derived, indicating whether or not the relative observations towards j are feasible. This means that node i is left to estimate the location of j only with the latter’s self position and without any relative observations. Deriving probability λ using CNNs modules of relevant automotive applications are discussed in the following Section.

Therefore, the goal of localization layer is to provide more accurate location awareness in terms of: i) global awareness,

Fig. 1. Example swarm of CAVs and processing architecture for each vehicle

i.e., target location vector $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} = \{\forall \mathbf{x}_i^{(t)} \in \mathcal{C}^{(t)}\} \in \mathbb{R}^{2|\mathcal{C}^{(t)}|}$ and ii) local awareness, i.e., target location vector $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} = \{\forall \mathbf{x}_i^{(t)} \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}\} \in \mathbb{R}^{2|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|}$. Each vehicle is able to estimate both target vectors in a distributed manner as Section IV will demonstrate.

III. ACCELERATED 3D SCENE ANALYSIS

Viewing the convolution operation as a series of dot-products between input and kernel vectors in an N -dimensional space (with N being the number of input/kernel channels), product quantization aims at reducing the number of required operations by splitting the initial space into S , N' -dimensional subspaces (where $N' = N/S$), and limiting the number of allowed representations in each one of them. To be more specific, the number of representations in each subspace is reduced via vector quantization (VQ), namely by approximating the original kernel sub-vectors using a small set of representatives called codewords (and their collection, a codebook). In doing so, product quantization approximates the original convolution using only dot-products between input and codewords, instead of the originals. Additionally, previous work on dictionary learning (DL) based MCA approaches [21], [22] has yielded promising acceleration outcomes with a negligible drop in accuracy. We evaluate the performance of the examined weight-sharing MCA techniques on the PointPillars network [6], which is designed for 3D object detection using LiDAR point clouds.

A. Training and evaluation

Our experiments were based on the KITTI 3D object detection [23] benchmark. 3716 annotated Velodyne point cloud scenes were used for training and 3769 annotated Velodyne point cloud scenes were used for testing and validation. For the deployment and fine-tuning of PointPillars we utilized the OpenPCDet framework [24]. Initial evaluation was based on a pre-trained instance of PointPillars, while for the retraining, the Adam optimizer was employed with learning rate $l_r = 0.003$, weight decay rate $D_W = 10^{-2}$ and a batch size $B = 4$. Training took place in the Geforce RTX 2080 with 16GB VRAM and compute capability 7.5.

B. Acceleration scheme

PointPillars [6] is a fully convolutional network, with its feature-extraction (backbone) stage being responsible for 97.7% of the total MAC operations required. In total, Pointpillars network encompasses 4.835×10^6 parameters and require

63.835×10^9 MACs. For a good balance between acceleration and accuracy loss, we only targeted the convolutional layers of the backbone network comprizing the second stage of PointPillars. Specifically, the targeted 2D- and 4×4 transposed 2D- convolutional layers, are responsible for approximately 47% and 44.4%, respectively, of the total required MACs. Acceleration was performed in 16 acceleration stages with each stage involving the quantization of a particular layer, followed by fine-tuning. Acceleration ratios of $\alpha = 10, 20, 30,$ and 40 on the targeted layers, lead to a reduction of the total required MACs by 82%, 86%, 88%, and 89%, or equivalently, to total model acceleration of PointPillars by $5.6\times, 7.6\times, 8.6\times,$ and $9.2\times,$ respectively.

C. Metrics

The official KITTI evaluation detection metrics include bird's eye view (BEV) mean average precision. The KITTI dataset is categorised into easy, moderate, and hard difficulties, and the official KITTI leaderboard is ranked by performance on moderate. Each 3D ground truth detection box is assigned to one out of three difficulty classes (*easy, moderate, hard*), and a 40-point Interpolated Average Precision metric is separately computed on each difficulty class, according to [25].

TABLE I
BEV MEAN AVERAGE PRECISION FOR CAR AND PEDESTRIAN CLASSES

	Car			Pedestrian		
	Easy	Moderate	Hard	Easy	Moderate	Hard
Original	92.04	88.06	86.66	61.60	56.01	52.05
DL, $\alpha = 5.6 \times$	91.83	87.32	84.72	56.45	51.00	46.93
DL, $\alpha = 7.6 \times$	92.03	87.40	84.73	56.46	50.18	46.22
DL, $\alpha = 8.6 \times$	91.76	86.80	84.08	53.49	47.14	43.71
DL, $\alpha = 9.2 \times$	92.57	85.10	83.67	51.04	44.79	41.91
VQ, $\alpha = 5.6 \times$	93.08	87.24	84.54	56.74	51.02	47.28
VQ, $\alpha = 7.6 \times$	91.90	86.74	84.20	54.11	47.84	43.82
VQ, $\alpha = 8.6 \times$	91.11	84.77	81.88	54.64	47.64	43.67
VQ, $\alpha = 9.2 \times$	91.75	86.41	82.44	50.81	44.94	41.53

Table I, summarizes the average precision (AP) for various acceleration ratios in the case of PointPillars. For Car and Pedestrian classes, the three APs correspond to the three levels of difficulty (namely, easy, moderate and hard) that the evaluation dataset provides. It is observed, as expected, that the impact on performance is greater as the acceleration ratios are increased, a tendency also observed for other values of acceleration ratios that are not depicted here. The relative performance drop is at most 1%, 3% and 5% for the three difficulty levels (easiest to hardest) of Car, while it varies between 18%-21% for Pedestrian. An indicative detection example is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. 3D vehicle detection with original and accelerated model

IV. COOPERATIVE AWARENESS SOLUTIONS FOR CAVS

In this Section, we describe in short two existing Cooperative Awareness (CA) solutions. The first one [17], called **GLLMS**, is an information diffusion based scheme which focuses on realizing the vision of global awareness, i.e., each vehicle to be location-aware of the entire cluster which belongs to. The second one [15], called **EKF-CA**, is a traditional distributed tracking scheme which exploits EKF in order to perform the local awareness task in a cost-effective way.

A. Information diffusion based scheme

Distributed localization diffusion aims to improve location accuracy through the combination of location vectors estimated by different nodes, though referring to the same target vector. More specifically, each node estimates the same target location vector, i.e., the locations of nodes of the cluster, by minimizing in a distributed manner a global centralized cost function. **GLLMS** algorithm has been proposed as a solution to this problem. Its two main steps for the case of node i and time instant t are shown below:

$$\psi_i^{(t,k+1)} = \tilde{x}_i^{(t,k)} - \mu_i^{(t)} \hat{L}_i^{(t)T} \left(\delta_i^{(t)} - \hat{L}_i^{(t)} \tilde{x}_i^{(t,k)} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$\tilde{x}_i^{(t,k+1)} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} c_{ij}^{(t)} \psi_j^{(t,k+1)} \quad (4)$$

Note that $\hat{L}_i^{(t)} = \begin{bmatrix} L_{i:}^{(t)} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & L_{:i}^{(t)} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2|\mathcal{C}^{(t)}|}$ with $L_{i:}^{(t)}$ being the i -th row of Laplacian matrix of cluster, indicating the connectivity links of node i . Differential coordinate measurement of $\delta_i^{(t)}$ is actually an average of relative observations of i . Small step size $\mu_i^{(t)} > 0$. At each time instant and for iteration $k + 1$, nodes broadcast and receive the estimations of the common parameter from their neighbors. Each node produces an intermediate estimation using Least-Means-Squares algorithm in (3), and updates it in (4) combining the intermediate estimations transmitted by its neighbors. Combination weights for each node sum up to 1. At the end of this iterative procedure, individual $\tilde{x}_i^{(t,k+1)}$ shall converge to the target $\tilde{x}^{(t)}$. See more details in [17].

B. Tracking based scheme

Although **GLLMS** is able to achieve high enough location accuracy, it does that at the cost of K required exchanges of measurements. For that reason, distributed **EKF-CA** has been proposed as an alternative low-cost CL solution, so as to enable i to be location-aware of its direct neighborhood. The following state-space model can be adopted for node i and its neighborhood:

$$\hat{x}_i^{(t)} = f(\hat{x}_i^{(t-1)}, \hat{u}_i^{(t)}) + \epsilon_i^{(t)}, \epsilon_i^{(t)} \sim \mathcal{G}(0, \mathbf{R}_i^{(t)}) \quad (5)$$

$$\hat{z}_i^{(t)} = h(\hat{x}_i^{(t)}) + w_i^{(t)}, w_i^{(t)} \sim \mathcal{G}(0, \mathbf{Q}_i^{(t)}) \quad (6)$$

Motion model $f(\cdot)$ acts as a rough prediction step of target state vector, employing control inputs like linear velocity and acceleration, angular velocity, yaw angle, etc. Control input vector $\hat{u}_i^{(t)}$ comprises of the control inputs of node i as well

as those transmitted to him from its neighboring nodes. In the same sense, measurement vector $\hat{z}_i^{(t)}$ contains the self positioning information of self node and its neighbors, as well as the relative observations of i towards each $j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}$ and vice versa. See more details about the involved quantities in [15]. Due to the non-linear form of motion and measurement models (5)-(6), EKF algorithm has been employed to derive the CA solution:

$$\bar{x}_i^{(t)} = f\left(\hat{x}_i^{(t-1)}, \hat{u}_i^{(t)}\right) \quad (7)$$

$$\bar{\Sigma}_i^{(t)} = F_i^{(t)} \hat{\Sigma}_i^{(t-1)} F_i^{(t)T} + R_i^{(t)} \quad (8)$$

$$K_i^{(t)} = \bar{\Sigma}_i^{(t)} H_i^{(t)T} \left(H_i^{(t)} \bar{\Sigma}_i^{(t)} H_i^{(t)T} + Q_i^{(t)} \right)^{-1} \quad (9)$$

$$\hat{x}_i^{(t)} = \bar{x}_i^{(t)} + K_i^{(t)} \left(\hat{z}_i^{(t)} - g\left(\bar{x}_i^{(t)}\right) \right) \quad (10)$$

$$\hat{\Sigma}_i^{(t)} = \left(\mathbb{I} - K_i^{(t)} H_i^{(t)} \right) \bar{\Sigma}_i^{(t)} \quad (11)$$

with $F_i^{(t)}$, $H_i^{(t)}$ the Jacobians of f and h . Therefore, each neighboring node transmit to i : i) self control inputs and positioning measurements, ii) all relative observations towards i . The latter, together with its own self and relative observations, follow (7)-(11) in order to be location-aware of its surrounding environment.

V. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND RESULTS

A. Simulation setup

The trajectories of 150 vehicles, within a simulation horizon $T = 448$ of time instances and time interval $dt = 0.4sec$ were extracted by CARLA [26]. A random ego vehicle along with the associated cluster is chosen for the evaluation, and its trajectory is shown in the heatmaps of Fig. 3. Assuming that vehicles communicate within a range of $30m$, the size of ego vehicle's neighborhood during the simulation ranges between 2 and 11, while cluster's size is between 2 and 97 vehicles. As far as the simulation parameters is concerned: $\sigma_o = 1m$ and $\sigma_a = 4^\circ$, for relative distance and angle measurements, $\Sigma_p = diag(3^2, 2.5^2)$ and $K = 30$. For evaluation metrics, we used the Location Awareness Error (LAE) as measured by vehicle i : $LAE_i^{(t)} = \sqrt{(1/N_i^{(t)}) \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} (LE_{j \leftarrow i}^{(t)})^2}$, where $LE_{j \leftarrow i}^{(t)}$ is the l_2 location error of j as measured by i and the overall Root Mean Square Error over time horizon T of LAE: $RT - LAE_i$.

B. Evaluation study

The APs of TABLE I indicate the probability λ of detection success when the original or accelerated model is employed in the perception layer. We have chosen three distinctive values of this parameter from the Car class evaluation, i.e., 92.04, 86.8 and 81.88%, corresponding to original model in Easy mode, DL with $\alpha = 8.6 \times$ model in Moderate mode and VQ with $\alpha = 8.6 \times$ model in Hard mode, respectively. Results are summarized in TABLE II. It is assumed that MDS is able to retrieve every possible squared distance among the nodes of the cluster, although in practice an approach for matrix completion of euclidean distance matrix is required.

TABLE II
RT-LAE (m) VS PROBABILITY λ OF DETECTION SUCCESS

CNN model	λ	GLLMS	EKF-CA	MDS	Noisy source
Original	92.04%	1.94	2.79	2.42	3.89
DL, $\alpha = 8.6 \times$	86.8%	2.16	3.13	2.42	3.89
VQ, $\alpha = 8.6 \times$	81.88%	2.18	3.20	2.42	3.89

For comparison reasons, MDS will not be affected by the probability λ . **GLLMS** is proven to be much superior than CA counterpart **EKF-CA** and centralized MDS in all three cases of detection success, reducing the RT-LAE of available noisy source by **50%** and **44%** in the best and worst case, highlighting the benefits of cooperation in localization task. **GLLMS** has an inherent mechanism of surpassing any lack of relative observations, i.e., the combination step (4) which fuses the estimated target vectors transmitted by neighbors. On the contrary, **EKF-CA** in the absence of relative observations is left only with the self positioning measurements of its neighbors, achieving **28%** and **17%** reduction of RT-LAE in the best and worst case. Since **GLLMS** doesn't exploit any noise statistics for estimating positions, covariance matrices of **EKF-CA** are also set to identity. The robustness of **GLLMS** in accelerated CNN's models is also verified in the heatmaps of Fig. 3, which visualize the trajectory of ego vehicle over time along with the individual localization error achieved by the related algorithm. Fig. 3 demonstrate that as for the CA

Fig. 3. Heatmaps of individual localization error using **GLLMS**

evaluation before, **GLLMS** is proven to be able to achieve almost a stable individual localization error for the ego vehicle over time, verifying once again the importance of combination step in location estimation accuracy.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper has contributed towards the realization of distributed intelligence for CAVs through a unified design of perception and localization layers. More specifically, in the perception layer a 3D object detection CNN has been employed, which is significantly accelerated by DL and VQ, without any critical reduction of detection success. The scene analysis and understanding indicators have been further integrated in the localization layer, so as to evaluate the ability of CL solutions against missing detections of nearby nodes. Information diffusion based scheme has proven to be superior, demonstrating its robust 4D awareness when accelerated CNNs are used.

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